

Joint Statement on Prenatal Multiple Loss and Recognition of Surviving Multiples

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In many healthcare systems, pregnancies that begin as multiple pregnancies but result in a singleton birth are inconsistently documented, leading to gaps in medical history and recognition. The following principles are intended to be applicable across diverse healthcare settings; however, implementation may vary according to national legislation, regulatory frameworks, and local clinical practice (Cabbage et al., 2025; Middlemiss, 2021). The International Council of Multiple Birth Organisations (ICOMBO) and the International Vanishing Twin Syndrome Foundation (IVTSF) believe:

- pregnancies that begin with more than one embryo must receive clinical, psychosocial, and familial recognition and, where feasible and consistent with local legal and regulatory frameworks, be documented within the medical record.
- surviving multiples following prenatal, perinatal, or infant loss must be recognised as part of a multiple birth set.
- families experiencing the loss of one or more multiples deserve clear, consistent, compassionate, and culturally sensitive communication that is responsive to individual preferences and cultural context.
- healthcare documentation systems must reflect the multiplicity of the original pregnancy and support the development of pathways that enable accurate, consistent reporting in alignment with national regulatory frameworks.
- surviving multiples and their families must have access to appropriate psychological, educational, and social supports throughout life as needed.
- healthcare systems must integrate recognition of prenatal and perinatal multiple loss into clinical practice, documentation systems, and family support services in a manner that respects individual preferences in communication, dignity, identity, and international diversity of practice.

Clinicians should actively assess individual needs through patient-centred communication, including preferences for language, level of information, emotional support, and recognition of the loss (Cabbage et al., 2025). These preferences may evolve over time and should be revisited throughout care. Care should be guided by the identification of individual family needs, preferences, and readiness for information, recognising that experiences and support needs following prenatal multiple loss vary widely.

Understanding the language of loss in multiple pregnancy

To ensure clear communication between families and healthcare providers, this statement defines and standardises terminology. Understanding these terms helps bridge the gap between medical necessity and the lived experience of families.

- Prenatal Multiple Loss: A broad term for the death of one or more babies during pregnancy, while at least one sibling survives.
- Vanishing Twin Syndrome (VTS): The death or cessation of development of a twin or higher order multiple(s) at any point in gestation. Despite the term “vanishing”, it is not guaranteed that the fetal tissue will fully disappear, and outcomes can vary (e.g., resorption, compression, or persistence of tissue), even in cases of first-trimester demise (Carlson & Mikes, 2025).
- Single Intrauterine Foetal Demise (IUFD): The death of one foetus later in a multiple pregnancy, typically after the first trimester.
- Selective Reduction (also referred to as multifetal pregnancy reduction) or Termination for Medical Reasons (TFMR): A complex clinical decision to end the development of one or more foetuses to protect the health of the remaining multiple(s) or the pregnant person.
- Co-multiple / Co-twin Survivor: The baby or babies who continue to develop and are born following the loss of their sibling(s).
- Chorionicity and Amnionicity: These terms describe whether babies share a placenta or an amniotic sac. These are the most critical factors for understanding medical risks to the survivor (s).
- Zygosity: Whether the multiples arise from a single fertilized egg (monozygotic; often referred to as “identical”) or separate fertilized eggs (dizygotic; often referred to as “non-identical”). While this is often unknown at the time of early loss, it remains part of the survivor(s)’ genetic context.

This position statement addresses all forms of prenatal loss within a multiple pregnancy, from the earliest weeks of gestation through to the later stages of pregnancy and birth.

Background:

Multiple-birth families represent a diverse and growing population globally, with experiences shaped by medical, psychosocial, cultural, and healthcare system factors. Across settings, families experiencing multiple pregnancies often navigate complex and evolving needs, particularly when outcomes differ among co-multiples. Multiple pregnancies are associated with increased medical, psychological, and social complexity for pregnant individuals, families, and surviving co-multiples. Advances in early ultrasound and the increasing use of assisted reproductive technologies (ART) have improved recognition of multifetal pregnancies and prenatal loss, while also highlighting that the implications of these losses may extend throughout pregnancy and beyond (Sun et al., 2017). Clinical management, surveillance, and counselling may differ in multiple pregnancies, particularly in cases involving shared placentation or other pregnancy-specific complications (Weitzner et al., 2023). The term “prenatal multiple loss” encompasses several distinct clinical scenarios, including vanishing twin syndrome, blighted ova, single intrauterine fetal demise later in pregnancy, selective fetal reduction or termination for medical reasons (TFMR), and losses associated with structural or chromosomal abnormalities. Although the clinical mechanisms, timing, and management of these losses may differ, they share the common feature of occurring within a multiple pregnancy in which one or more fetuses do not survive while one or more continue to develop.

Pregnancy loss at any gestational stage may have profound emotional, relational, and psychological impacts. In the context of multiple pregnancy, families may additionally experience overlapping processes of grief and continuing attachment, evolving parental identity, clinical uncertainty, and concerns related to surviving co-multiples. While the clinical implications of prenatal multiple loss vary according to timing and circumstance, these experiences may influence healthcare decision-making, documentation, screening interpretation, and the longer-term experiences of maternal and child patients (Batsry & Yinon, 2022; Lee et al., 2023).

Most pregnancy losses, including those occurring in multiple gestations, occur prenatally and are most common in the first trimester (Batsry & Yinon, 2022; Petrini et al., 2016). As a result, multiple status at birth (e.g. twin, triplet, higher-order multiple, or singleton) does not necessarily reflect the number of embryos present earlier in pregnancy. In many settings, early pregnancy losses occurring prior to formal entry into maternity or perinatal care systems may not be systematically captured within national health datasets, limiting epidemiological visibility and continuity of medical documentation (Middlemiss, 2021). When a loss is not formally documented, it may feel to families as though that baby was never acknowledged within the healthcare system (Boutillier et al., 2023; Cabbage et al., 2025). This contributes not only to under-recognition in health records and research datasets but also to missed opportunities for compassionate, patient-centred care. As a result, the true prevalence and long-term clinical and psychosocial implications of prenatal multiple loss may remain under-recognised within both healthcare systems and population-level datasets.

Families, however, frequently experience significant grief and emotional impact following the loss of one or more babies in a multiple pregnancy (Cabbage et al., 2025; Bryan et al., 2002; Richards et al., 2015). This unique journey often leads to feelings of isolation, where parents may require direction toward peer support networks to find a sense of belonging through shared lived experience (Ernst et al., 2025). In the absence of clear guidance from healthcare systems, many turn to peer support networks to find validation, shared understanding, and a sense of belonging through lived experience (Ernst et al., 2025).

Accurate recognition of pregnancies that began as multiples in gestation is important for:

- respecting the lived experience of families
- supporting continuity of medical history
- acknowledging the relational and developmental context of surviving multiples
- appropriate psychological, psychosocial, educational, peer, and social supports, including access to multidisciplinary care teams where available across the continuum of care.

In addition, documenting early multiple pregnancy has direct clinical relevance for:

- interpretation of prenatal screening tests (e.g. cfDNA/NIPT), where residual placental or fetal DNA from a demised co-twin may influence screening accuracy and counselling considerations
- obstetric risk assessment and pregnancy management
- interpretation of placental pathology findings, particularly in pregnancies involving shared placentation or evidence of prior fetal demise
- genetic counselling considerations, including counselling regarding uncertain or discordant prenatal screening findings, residual cfDNA from a demised twin, and questions surrounding zygosity or biological origins.

This position aligns with the ICOMBO Declaration of Rights and Statement of Needs of Twins and Higher Order Multiples, which affirms the importance of recognition, dignity, and appropriate recording of multiple births and losses (ICOMBO, 2022). Accurate recording of key characteristics of a multiple pregnancy remains essential, as affirmed in the Declaration. This includes documentation of the placenta type, whether the babies share a placenta, whether they share an amniotic sac, and, where possible, whether they are identical or non-identical twins (Khalil et al., 2025). In clinical terminology, these characteristics are referred to as placentation, chorionicity, amnionicity, and zygosity, and they are important for understanding medical risks and the potential impact of the loss of one foetus on the surviving co-multiple (ICOMBO, 2023). In many pregnancies, particularly when prenatal loss occurs, zygosity cannot be determined antenatally and may remain unknown unless postnatal genetic testing is performed. Where uncertainty exists, documentation must clearly reflect this. In multifetal pregnancies involving prenatal or perinatal loss, zygosity may be indeterminate; such uncertainty must be clearly documented (Craig et al., 2019). Chorionicity directly determines risk to the surviving foetus following the death of a co-twin (Dessole et al., 2026). Accurate documentation of placentation and chorionicity is also clinically important because these features influence risk and management in multifetal pregnancies (Khalil et al., 2025). Following a single foetal demise, risks to the surviving co-twin differ significantly by chorionicity. Contemporary evidence indicates that monochorionic pregnancies are associated with

substantially higher risks of co-twin death, preterm birth, and adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes compared with dichorionic pregnancies (Dessole et al., 2026).

Respect for the individual requires recognition of genetic identity as integral to dignity, well-being, and protection from harm arising from misinformation or incomplete documentation. In the context of prenatal multiple loss, incomplete or absent recognition of a co-twin may have lasting implications for the surviving child, including their developing sense of identity, psychological well-being, and understanding of their biological origins (Batsry & Yinon, 2022; Song et al., 2020). This aligns with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights, which affirms the right of individuals to access information about their genetic identity and positions accurate recognition and documentation as a matter of fundamental human rights (UNESCO, 1997). Accurate and transparent documentation is, therefore, not only clinically relevant but also supports the individual's right to access information about their own beginnings. Improved recognition and standardised documentation may also support future epidemiological research, health surveillance efforts, and understanding of the long-term implications of prenatal multiple loss.

Minimum Standards for Clinical Communication

In pregnancies affected by prenatal or perinatal multiple loss, communication must be intentional, consistent, and trauma-informed. Care is delivered by an interdisciplinary team, which may include obstetricians, maternal-fetal medicine specialists, nurses, midwives, psychologists, social workers, bereavement specialists, genetic counsellors, and community-based support organisations. These professionals often serve as primary points of contact, offering ongoing support, guidance, and coordination for families.

Care should also reflect a family health and well-being perspective, recognising not only the clinical implications of loss but also the strengths, resilience, and evolving needs of families over time. Supporting families requires sustained, coordinated care that promotes long-term health and well-being across both clinical and community contexts.

The following practices are recommended as minimum standards of care and will inform the development of patient-facing resources outlining what families can expect from care:

1. Acknowledge the loss alongside the surviving embryo(s) or foetus(es)

Where appropriate, recognise the loss of one or more embryos or foetuses, even when one or more survive. Clinical communication often focuses on the surviving foetus to provide reassurance; however, this may unintentionally minimise the loss. Providers should create space for the coexistence of grief and hope and recognise that families are likely to be mourning one baby while continuing the pregnancy with another, and responses may vary widely in their complexity.

2. Standardise documentation and narrative across the care team

Medical records must clearly reflect that the pregnancy began as a multiple pregnancy, and this information must be consistently communicated across all members of the care team with family consent. Families should not be required to repeatedly reintroduce or justify their loss. Standardised documentation supports continuity of care, reduces distress, and ensures that the loss is recognised at every stage of care.

3. Use clear, humanising, and family-centred language

Language must validate the significance of the loss for the patient and reflect that the pregnancy involved more than one baby, even when only one may remain visible and/or the loss has occurred early in pregnancy.

4. Provide anticipatory guidance on clinical and developmental implications

Clinicians must explain how the loss of a co-multiple may affect pregnancy management, birth planning, and potential long-term outcomes for the surviving child(ren). This not only supports informed decision-making but also validates that the loss has ongoing clinical and developmental relevance. Individuals navigating complex clinical decisions in multifetal pregnancy, particularly in the context of selective reduction, may experience significant emotional and psychological burden; evidence suggests that decision-making in these contexts is often challenging and that support needs may extend well beyond the duration of the pregnancy (Beriwal et al., 2020).

5. Support identity recognition when appropriate

When desired by the family, clinicians must be attentive to how families and surviving children understand and describe their experience (e.g. identifying as a singleton, twin, or multiple).

6. Offer specific, ongoing, and appropriately targeted support resources, including emotional, practical, and specialist services, based on individual family needs

Clinicians (i.e., doctors, nurses, midwives, and other health professionals) must provide support beyond the immediate clinical setting where needed. These professionals are often the primary providers of ongoing, family-centred care and play a key role in guiding families through both clinical and community-based support systems. Support should be

responsive to individual family needs and recognise family strengths, resilience, and existing support networks. Framing support as ongoing rather than one-time reinforces that family needs may evolve over time and that care should promote long-term health and well-being.

7. Validate identity and terminology with families

Clinicians may ask parents (and, when appropriate, surviving children), how they understand and describe their experience (e.g. identifying as a twin or part of a multiple pregnancy) and reflect this language in clinical documentation where appropriate.

Recognition of identity can be an important component of psychological well-being and long-term adjustment.

8. Integrate trauma-informed care into all clinical interactions

Clinical staff (e.g., doctors, nurses, midwives, and other health professionals) should be trained to acknowledge the loss prior to examinations or discussions focused on the surviving fetus.

9. Incorporate culturally responsive care

Care teams must remain sensitive to cultural, religious, and personal beliefs regarding pregnancy, loss, and personhood. Communication and care practices must be adapted where possible to align with family values while maintaining clinical clarity and transparency. Care should also recognise and build upon family strengths and support systems, promoting resilience and long-term well-being.

10. Recognise and support the central role of nurses and midwives in family-centred care

Nurses, midwives, and public health nurses are essential providers of family-centred care in pregnancies affected by multiple loss. They frequently serve as consistent points of contact across hospital and community settings, offering clinical guidance, emotional support, and continuity of care. Care models should recognise and support this role, and ensure that nurses are equipped, included in communication pathways, and empowered to meet the complex and evolving needs of multiple-birth families.

These practices must be integrated into standard obstetric care pathways to ensure that prenatal and perinatal multiple loss is consistently recognised, documented, and addressed across the continuum of care.

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Supplementary Appendix A

Support Resources for Families Experiencing a Loss of Multiples During Pregnancy and Postpartum

This appendix provides a curated list of international and country-specific organisations offering support for families and individuals affected by prenatal and perinatal loss in multiple pregnancy. Resources include peer support networks, bereavement services, and educational materials for both families and clinicians.

International Organisations

These organisations provide support, advocacy, and resources across multiple countries.

- International Council of Multiple Birth Organisations (ICOMBO)
<https://icombo.org>
- Center for Loss in Multiple Birth (CLIMB), Inc.
<https://www.climb-support.org>
- Twinless Twins Support Group International (TTSGI)
<https://twinlesstwins.org>
- Lone Twin Network
<https://www.lonetwinnetwork.org.uk>
- International Vanishing Twin Syndrome Foundation (IVTSF)
<https://vanishingtwinsyndrome.org>
- Footprints Baby Loss Support
<https://footprintsbabyloss.org/>
- Empty Arms Bereavement Support – Twin Loss Support Group
<https://www.emptyarmsbereavement.org/twin-loss-support-group>
- National Child Traumatic Stress Network (NCTSN) – Sibling Death and Childhood Traumatic Grief
https://www.nctsn.org/sites/default/files/resources/sibling_death_and_childhood_traumatic_grief_families.pdf
- Twins Trust Bereavement Service
<https://twinstrust.org/bereavement.html>
- The Lullaby Trust – If a Twin or Multiple Dies
<https://www.lullabytrust.org.uk/bereavement-support/practical-advice/if-a-twin-or-multiple-dies>
- Neonatal Butterfly Project – Support Resources for Clinicians and Families
<https://www.neonatalbutterflyproject.org/resources/links-support-groups/>
- Twin to Twin Transfusion Syndrome Foundation
<https://ttsfoundation.org/>
- Skye High Foundation
<https://www.theskyehighfoundation.com/>
- Sands
<https://www.sands.org.uk/>

Notes on Use:

- Availability and scope of services may vary by region.
- Families may benefit from referral to both local (country-specific) and international peer support networks, depending on availability and preference.

- Clinicians should consider individual family needs, cultural context, and preferred forms of support when making referrals.

Supporting Organisations and Individuals

If you are interested in being listed as a supporting organisation or individual, please complete [this form](#).